

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Paper

Evaluation Of Drug-Drug Interactions in A Hospitalized Patients: A Prospective Observational Study

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 29 May 2026

Keywords:

Drug-drug interactions,
polypharmacy, medication
safety, hospitalized patients

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.20443312

ABSTRACT

Background: Adverse drug reactions are largely caused by drug-drug interactions (DDIs), especially in hospitalized patients taking several medications. The risk of clinically significant interactions is greatly increased by polypharmacy, advanced age, and comorbid conditions, which can result in higher morbidity, mortality, longer hospital stays, and higher healthcare costs. **Objective :** To evaluate the prevalence, pattern, and severity of drug–drug interactions among hospitalized patients in a tertiary care hospital. **Materials and Methods:** At Sri Balaji Medical Care Hospital, a prospective observational study was carried out over a ten-month period. There were 98 hospitalized patients over the age of 15 from different departments. Every day, patient case records were examined to gather medication profiles and demographic information. A drug interaction checker was used to evaluate drug-drug interactions, and mean \pm standard deviation was used to analyze the drug. **Results:** Among the 98 study subjects, females constituted 53% and males 47%. The highest prevalence of DDIs was observed in the 61–80 years age group (33%). Combination interactions were more common than single interactions, with minor–moderate combinations accounting for 58.1% of cases. Overall, minor interactions were most frequent (48%), followed by moderate (39%) and major interactions (13%). Frequently identified interacting drug classes included antibiotics, cardiovascular drugs, and central nervous system agents. Clinically significant major interactions included combinations associated with QT prolongation, hyperkalemia, thrombogenicity, and CNS depression. **Conclusion:** The study demonstrates a high prevalence of potential drug–drug interactions among hospitalized patients, especially in elderly individuals and patients receiving multiple medications. Although most interactions were minor to moderate, the occurrence of major interactions highlights the importance of regular medication review, early DDI screening, and active involvement of clinical pharmacists to improve patient safety and optimize therapeutic outcomes.

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

INTRODUCTION

A drug is a substance that is administered to the body in order to have a biological effect. By attaching to a receptor or changing an enzyme's activity, for example, it modifies one or more biochemical processes¹. Drug interactions may cause serious unwanted effects or decrease the effectiveness of certain medications. This risk is greatly increased by polypharmacy, which is especially common in elderly patients². It is surprising to examine a patient in the modern era of medicine receiving only one or two drugs at a time. Drug interactions are influenced by the coexistence of several medical disorders as well as the necessity and practice of polypharmacy. A drug interaction occurs when one or more medications, foods, or beverages are administered simultaneously, changing the nature or effect of the drugs. One well-known factor influencing drug responsiveness and a major contributor to adverse drug responses is drug-drug interaction³. According to reports, between 4 and 5 percent of hospital inpatients are prescribed medications that may interfere. The majority of these possible drug interactions might not happen or might go unnoticed. Drug interactions were responsible for 234 (6.9%) of the 3600 (4.3%) adverse drug responses found in 83,000 drug exposures in a large surveillance effort⁴. Medication-related harm remains a significant issue among older adults, with nearly half experiencing adverse health outcomes linked to potential drug exposure. Of these events, approximately 35–59% are considered preventable, highlighting the need for improved prescribing practices, careful monitoring, and strategies to minimize risks associated with medication use in this population⁵. Drug interaction broadly classified into two types ;1. Pharmacokinetics interaction: Absorption interaction, Distribution interaction, Metabolism interaction, Excretion interaction

2. Pharmacodynamic interaction: Direct pharmacodynamic interaction, Indirect pharmacodynamic interaction⁶.

Drug interactions can have negative impacts on quality of life, length of hospital stay, morbidity, death, and health care costs⁷. Common risk factors associated with drug–drug interactions (DDIs) include patient-related factors such as age and gender, alterations in pharmacokinetic processes, the use of multiple medications (polypharmacy), medication errors, and the presence of comorbid conditions⁸. Drug-related problems are a frequent cause of illness (morbidity) and, in severe cases it can contribute to death (Mortality)⁹. Polypharmacy can lead to a “prescribing cascade,” where an adverse drug reaction is misinterpreted, prompting the prescription of additional, potentially unnecessary medications, which in turn increases the patient’s risk of experiencing further adverse drug reactions¹⁰. As age increases, the occurrence of multiple coexisting diseases often necessitates prescribing several medications to a single patient. Consequently, a typical 65-year-old patient is likely to be taking around five medications at the same time¹¹. Medications most often involved in significant potential interactions are those routinely used in the everyday clinical care of elderly patients with chronic conditions¹². Exposure to drug–drug interactions (DDIs), especially those that heighten the risk of bleeding, significantly raises the probability of older adults being admitted to the hospital due to adverse drug reactions. Careful monitoring and management of such interactions are essential to reduce preventable hospitalizations and improve medication safety in this population¹³. Drug–drug interactions (DDIs) can lead to blood pressure fluctuations, sedation, central nervous system toxicity, cardiac arrhythmias, and other complications. Due to factors like long-term therapy and polypharmacy, preventing DDIs in these patients is challenging, posing significant

difficulties for physicians in managing their treatment safely and effectively¹⁴. The concomitant use of NSAIDs and warfarin should be avoided, especially in patients over 65 or those with risk factors for NSAID-induced gastropathy, such as peptic ulcer history, steroid use, heavy smoking, or high NSAID doses. One study found a 13-fold increased risk of haemorrhagic peptic ulcers in these patients¹⁵.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

It is a prospective study and was conducted in departments of Sri Balaji medical Care hospital (SBMHC), Renigunta, Tirupathi. The study was carried out on above 15 years age group of either sex for period of 10 months

The total of 98 subjects of all departments were enrolled in the study. for the collection of the data, the case record files of all the patients admitted in the departments were thoroughly reviewed each day during the study period.

The information recorded included the demographic details of patients, details about medications being used. The drug- drug interactions were assessed by using the drug interaction checker. The data were stored in the Microsoft excel and were analyzed by using the mean \pm standard deviation.

RESULTS

The demographic details and characteristics of the patients indicate a female predominance, with 52 out of 98 subjects (53%) being female and 46 (47%) males. The most common age group was 61– 80 years, comprising 32 patients (33%), followed by the 21-40 and 41-60 age groups each had % of the patients (28 subjects). The 0-20years age group with 7 patients (7 %). while those above 80 years accounted for 3.1% (3 subjects). Regarding subjects noted combination of drug interactions were a majority of cases, comprising 57 subjects, showed minor to moderate interactions. Total of 17 subjects (17.3%) experienced a combination of minor, moderate, and major drug interactions. Additionally, 4(4.1%) subjects experienced moderate and major interactions while 3(3.1%) subjects experienced minor and major interactions. Among the study subjects, single drug interactions were observed with minor interactions in 12(12.2%) subjects, moderate in 4(4.1%) subjects, and major in 1(1.1%) subject. Among 98 subjects, drug interactions were predominantly minor (73) 48%, followed by moderate (60) 39%, while major interactions (19) 13% were least common.

sno	Details	Characteristics	No. of subjects	Total
1.	Gender	Male Female	46(47%) 52(53%)	98(100%)
2.	Age	0 – 20 years AGE GROUP 21 – 40 years AGE GROUP 41 – 60 years AGE GROUP 61- 80 years AGE GROUP 81 – 100 years AGE GROUP	7(7%) 28(28.5%) 28(28.5%) 32(33%) 3(3%)	98(100%)
3.	Subjects noted combination of drug interactions	Minor –Moderate – major Minor –Moderate Minor – Major Moderate – major	17(17.3%) 57(58.1%) 3(3.1%) 4(4.1%)	98(100%)
	Subjects noted single drug interaction	Minor Major Moderate	12(12.2%) 1(1.1%) 4(4.1%)	

4.	Total no. of drug interactions	Minor Moderate Major	71(48%) 58(39%) 19(13%)	148(100%)
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Sn o	description	Drug interaction	severity	In total
1	One drug may decrease the excretion rate of another drug which could result in a higher serum level	Acetaminophen + levofloxacin Cefpodoxime proxetil +Acetaminophen Furosemide + levofloxacin Cefpodoxime + levocetizine Cefpodoxime + pantoprazole Cefperazone + pantoprazole Acetaminophen + Sulbactam Pantoprazole + Sulbactam Cefperazone + acetaminophen Pantoprazole + Acetaminophen Acetylcysteine + fexofenadine Sucralfate + levosalbutamol Doxycycline + acetaminophen Aceclofenac + doxycycline Ceftriaxone + tramadol Tramadol + pantoprazole Ceftriaxone + pantoprazole Acetaminophen + amoxicillin Aceclofenac + amoxicillin Cefoperazone + tramadol Nitrofurantoin + Flavoxate Aceclofenac + Metoclopramide Aceclofenac + Pantoprazole Tazobactam + Levofloxacin Ceftriaxone + Acetaminophen Paracetamol + Ringers lactate Lorazepam + levofloxacin Furosemide + pantoprazole Acetaminophen + meropenem Pregabalin + doxycycline Furosemide + ceftriaxone Ciprofloxacin + meropenem Acetaminophen + rabeprazole Aceclofenac + rabeprazole Aceclofenac + pregabalin	minor	45

		Pregabalin + acetaminophen Pregabalin + rabeprazole Mefenamic acid + pantoprazole Pantoprazole + dicyclomine Acetaminophen + dicyclomine Aceclofenac + dicyclomine Mefenamic acid + amoxicillin Dicyclomine + amoxicillin Linezolid + aceclofenac Metformin + amoxicillin		
		Valproate + lorazepam Ticagrelor + sitagliptin Piperacillin + levofloxacin Glimepiride + Telmisartan Pantoprazole + piperacillin Pantoprazole + Tazobactam Azithromycin + deflazacort Ceftriaxone + amikacin Tramadol + Amikacin Pantoprazole + amikacin Ceftriaxone + dexamethasone Furosemide + tazobactam Ranolazine + metoprolol	Moderate	13
		Metronidazole + amiodarone	major	1
2	One drug may increase the excretion rate of another which could result in a lower serum level and potentially a reduction in efficacy.	Furosemide + Acetaminophen Spironolactone + Metformin Spironolactone + sitagliptin	minor	3
		Torsemide + folic acid	Moderate	1
3	One drug may increase the hypotensive activities of another drug	Labetalol + Furosemide Torsemide + spironolactone Chlorthalidone + Acetaminophen Chlorthalidone + Amlodipine Chlorthalidone + Telmisartan Metoprolol + nitroglycerin	minor	6
4	The risk or severity of hypertension can be increased when one drug is combined with another drug	Phenylephrine + levosalbutamol Linezolid + mefenamic acid	Minor	2
5	The risk or severity of QTc prolongation can be increased when one drug is combined with another drug	Azithromycin + Levocetirizine Bilastine + Azitromycin	minor	2
		Pregabalin + domperidone Metronidazole + domperidone	Moderate	2
		Azithromycin + domperidone Levofloxacin + valproate sodium	major	2
6	The risk or severity of Tachycardia can be increased when one drug is combined with another drug	Ipratropium + formoterol fumarate Glycopyrronium bromide + levosalbutamol	minor	2
		Ipratropium bromide + glycopyrronium bromide	major	1
7		Torsemide + Telmisartan	minor	2

	The therapeutic efficacy of one drug can be decreased when used in combination with another drug	Torsemide + Metformin		
		Nortriptyline + domperidone Glimepiride + Torsemide	moderate	2
8	The therapeutic efficacy of one drug can be increased when used in combination with another drug	Pregabalin + nortriptyline Metoprolol + vildagliptin	moderate	2
9	The metabolism of one drug can be decreased when combined with another drug	Amlodipine + Azithromycin Montelukast + dextromethorphan Metformin + cilostazol Atorvastatin + cilastazol Ticagrelor + valsartan	Minor	5
		Montelukast + naproxen Naproxen + domperidone Metronidazole + tramadol Metronidazole + ondansetron Montelukast + domperidone Labetalol + Ondansetron Labetalol + Acetaminophen Acetaminophen + Montelukast Levofloxacin + Doxofylline Acetaminophen + Doxofylline Acetaminophen + Ondansetron Domperidone + doxofylline Acetaminophen + metronidazole Domperidone + acetaminophen Dexamethasone + tramadol Ciprofloxacin + metronidazole Ciprofloxacin + pantoprazole Clopidogrel + rosuvastatin Torasemide + rosuvastatin	moderate	19
		Tamsulosin + clonidine Ciprofloxacin + acetaminophen Ciprofloxacin + ondansetron Clopidogrel + torsemide	major	4
10.	The metabolism of Azithromycin can be increased when one drug combined with another drug	Acetaminophen + Azithromycin Hydrocortisone + tramadol Dexamethasone + metronidazole Clindamycin + acetaminophen	moderate	4
		Theophylline + hydrocortisone Dexamethasone + pantoprazole Nortriptyline + acetaminophen	Major	3
11.	The risk or severity of adverse effects can be increased when one drug is combined with another drug	Ceftriaxone + Ringers lactate Spironolactone + sacubitril	minor	2
		Calcium gluconate + ceftriaxone Mefenamic acid + aceclofenac	Moderate	2
		Dexamethasone + hydrocortisone	Major	1
12.	The risk or severity of gastrointestinal bleeding can be increased when one drug	Nortriptyline + aceclofenac	minor	1

	is combined with another drug			
13.	Pantoprazole can cause a decrease in the absorption of doxycycline resulting in a reduced serum concentration and potentially a decrease in efficacy	Pantoprazole + doxycycline	moderate	1
14.	The risk or severity of serotonin syndrome can be increased when ondansetron is combined with tramadol	Ondansetron + tramadol	moderate	1
15.	The risk or severity of CNS depression can be increased when one drug is combined with another drug	Lorazepam + levetiracetam Valproate sodium + levetiracetam Phenytoin + levetiracetam	moderate	3
16.	The risk or severity of angioedema can be increased when one drug is combined with another drug	Valsartan + sitagliptin Sitagliptin + sacubitril	moderate	2
17.	The risk or severity of hypokalemia can be increased when one drug is combined with another drug	Hydrocortisone + Furosemide Deflazacort + Doxofyllin Budesonide + levosalbutamol Deflazacort + doxofylline	Moderate	4
18.	The risk or severity of hyperkalemia can be increased when one drug is combined with another drug	Telmisartan + Spironolactone Valsartan + spironolactone	major	2
19.	Progesterone may increase the thrombogenic activities of tranexamic	Progesterone + tranexamic acid	Major	1
20.	The risk or severity of tendinopathy can be increased when Deflazacort is combined with Levofloxacin.	Deflazacort + levofloxacin	Moderate	1
21.	Levosalbutamol may increase the sympathomimetic activities of Formoterol.	Levosalbutamol + formoterol fumarate	Moderate	1
22.	Tranexamic acid may increase the thrombogenic activities of calcium	Tranexamic acid + calcium	major	1
23.	The risk or severity of sedation can be increased when drug is combined with another drug	Clonidine + nortriptyline Clonidine + gabapentin	Major	2
24.	Nortriptyline may increase the orthostatic hypotensive, hypotensive, and	Nortriptyline + tamsulosin	major	1

	antihypertensive activities of Tamsulosin			
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DISCUSSION

- In the present study, the highest proportion of DDIs occurred in patients aged 61–80 years (33%), indicating that elderly patients are the most vulnerable group. This finding aligns with Khaiser et al., who found that the 70–79-year age group had the highest prevalence of polypharmacy-associated DDIs. Both studies confirm that advancing age is strongly associated with increased DDI risk due to multiple comorbidities, altered drug metabolism, and reduced organ function.
- This study observed a slight female predominance (53%) in DDI occurrence, similar to Khaiser et al., where females also showed a slightly higher prevalence of polypharmacy (53.84%) than males. This similarity may reflect increased healthcare utilization and greater chronic medication exposure among women.
- Minor interactions were most frequent in the current study, while major interactions were less common but clinically significant. This trend aligns with Georgiev et al. (2022), who also reported that most hospitalized patient DDIs are minor-to-moderate, whereas severe interactions are fewer but require urgent clinical attention.
- In this study, combination interactions (especially minor–moderate combinations, 58.1%) were more common than single interactions, strongly suggesting that polypharmacy is the principal driver of DDI occurrence. Khaiser et al. similarly demonstrated that patients receiving ≥ 5 drugs had significantly higher DDI prevalence. This reinforces the established relationship

between increasing medication count and exponential rise in interaction probability.

- In this study found frequent interactions involving:

Antibiotics (azithromycin, levofloxacin, ceftriaxone), Cardiovascular drugs (telmisartan, spironolactone, metoprolol), CNS drugs (nortriptyline, clonidine, pregabalin). This is consistent with the systematic review by Oliveira et al. (2020), which identified cardiovascular agents, diuretics, antimicrobials, and CNS drugs as the most common classes implicated in hospitalized elderly DDIs. □

CONCLUSION

The present study highlights the significant prevalence of drug–drug interactions among hospitalized patients, with a total of 98 subjects evaluated. A higher proportion of cases was observed in females, and the elderly age group (61–80 years) was most affected, emphasizing the impact of age and polypharmacy on interaction risk.

The majority of drug interactions were of minor and moderate severity, with minor interactions being the most common overall. Combination drug interactions were more frequently observed than single interactions, particularly minor to moderate combinations, indicating the influence of multiple drug use in clinical practice. Although major interactions were less frequent, their presence underscores the need for careful monitoring due to potential serious clinical outcomes.

These findings reinforce that polypharmacy and advancing age are key risk factors for drug interactions. Early identification, regular

medication review, and the use of drug interaction screening tools are essential to minimize adverse effects. Clinical pharmacists and healthcare professionals play a crucial role in improving medication safety, reducing preventable adverse drug reactions, and optimizing therapeutic outcomes.

REFERENCES

1. Sam Baron; Sara Linton; Maureen A O'Malley, On Drugs-PMC 2023.
2. Thomsen LA; Winterstein AG; Sondergaard B; Haugbolle LS; Melander, A. Systematic review of the incidence and characteristics of preventable adverse drug events in ambulatory care 2007.
3. Madhav Mutalik; Dhara Sanghavi, Review Of Drug Interactions: A Comprehensive Update 2014.
4. Quinn DI; Day RO, Clinically Important Drug Interactions. In: Speight TM, Holford HG, Editors. Avery's Drug Treatment. 4th Ed. Auckland: Adis International; 1997.
5. Parekh N, Ali K, Page A, Roper T, Rajkumar C. Incidence of medication-related harm in older adults after hospital discharge: a systematic review 2018.
6. Priyanka Vitthal Kshirsagar; Pratiksha Suresh Nemane; Arati Suresh Khose; Omkar Bappadaheb Nalwade, A Review On Drug Interaction 2024.
7. B. Guthrie; B.Makubate; V. Hernandez-Santiago; Creischulte, The Rising Tide Of Polypharmacy And Drug-Drug Interactions: Population Database Analysis 1995-2010. 2015
8. M. Ismail; Z. Iqbal; M.B. Khattak; A. Javaid; M.I. Khan , Potential drug-drug interactions in psychiatric ward of a tertiary care hospital: prevalence, levels and association with risk factors 2012.
9. D.A. Roy; I. Shanfar; P. Shenoy, Drug-related problems among chronic kidney disease patients: a pharmacist-led study
10. Rochon PA; Gurwitz JH; Optimising drug treatment for elderly people: The prescribing cascade 1997.
11. Gallagher PF; Barry PJ; Ryan C; Hartigan I; O'Mahony D, Inappropriate prescribing in an acutely ill population of elderly patients as determined by Beers' Criteria. Age Ageing 2008.
12. Seymour R M; Routledge P, A. Important drug-drug interactions in the elderly. Drugs and Aging 1998.
13. Hughes JE; Moriarty F; Bennett KE; Cahir C, Drug-drug interactions and the risk of adverse drug reaction-related hospital admissions in the older population 2023.
14. H.B. Mezgebe, K. Sied, Prevalence of potential drug-drug interactions among psychiatric patients in a referral hospital, mekelle, Tigray, Ethiopia 2015.
15. Shorr RI; Ray WA; Daugherty JR; Griffin MR, Concurrent use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and oral anticoagulants places elderly persons at high risk for haemorrhagic peptic ulcer disease 1993.

HOW TO CITE: O. Kavya, O. Saraswathi, C. Mohana Evaluation of drug-drug interactions in a hospitalized patients: A prospective observational study, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2026, Vol 4, Issue 5, 7829-7837, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20443312>

